

Hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of novel hydrazone derivatives in experimental models of hepatotoxicity *in vitro*

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Received 21 November 2025 ♦ Accepted 25 December 2025 ♦ Published 27 January 2026

Citation: Stefanova D, Kondeva-Burdina M, Tzankova D, Garip A, Georgieva M, Tzankova V (2026) Hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity of novel hydrazone derivatives in experimental models of hepatotoxicity *in vitro*. Pharmacia 73: 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e179317>

Abstract

The safety profile of two newly synthesized series of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}) was studied in different liver-derived cell and subcellular culture models, i.e., isolated rat liver hepatocytes and microsomes, and the HepG2 cell line. The hydrazones, which have previously been reported to possess neuroprotective and antioxidant activity, were further assessed for possible hepatoprotective and antioxidant properties in several *in vitro* models of hepatotoxicity: non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation in isolated rat liver microsomes; metabolic bioactivation induced by carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄, 86 μM) in rat hepatocytes; and oxidative stress models induced by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH, 75 μM) in rat hepatocytes and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 0.1 mM) in HepG2 cells. Compounds 7d and 8d demonstrated the lowest hepatotoxic potential in isolated rat liver microsomes and hepatocytes. In HepG2 cells, all tested hydrazones exhibited low or negligible *in vitro* toxicity, with IC₅₀ values ranging from 64.28 to 205.10 μM. Compound 7c showed the lowest cytotoxicity, followed by 7a and 8d. All hydrazones exhibited significant antioxidant activity under conditions of non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation, with 7d and 8d displaying the most pronounced effects. In the CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity model, all compounds demonstrated statistically significant hepatoprotective and antioxidant activity, as evidenced by improved hepatocyte viability, reduced lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage, preserved intracellular glutathione (GSH) levels, and decreased malondialdehyde (MDA) production. Similar protective trends were observed in the model of t-BuOOH-induced oxidative stress, again with 7d and 8d showing superior effects. In the H₂O₂-induced oxidative stress model in HepG2 cells, compounds 7c, 7d, 7e, 8d, and 8e exhibited protective activity, with 7e and 8d providing the strongest protection. Overall, compounds 7d and 8d emerged as the most promising candidates, combining low hepatotoxicity with pronounced hepatoprotective and antioxidant effects, supporting their potential for further pharmacological development.

Keywords

Antioxidant properties, hepatoprotective activity, hydrazone derivatives, *in vitro* hepatotoxicity, oxidative stress

Introduction

Oxidative stress is a major pathogenic mechanism underlying many liver disorders. It results from an imbalance between the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and cellular antioxidant defense capacity. Excessive accumulation of ROS can initiate lipid peroxidation, leading to membrane destabilization, mitochondrial dysfunction, and eventually hepatocyte necrosis or apoptosis. Therefore, the discovery and evaluation of novel compounds capable of maintaining redox homeostasis and protecting liver cells from oxidative damage remain crucial in modern pharmacological research.

Pyrrroles and their derivatives are among the most important classes of nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds due to their wide range of biological activities, including antibacterial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, and antioxidant effects (Hm and Dubey 2024). In recent years, numerous studies on pyrrole-based structures incorporating amide or hydrazone functionalities have demonstrated strong antioxidant and radical-scavenging potential, often exceeding that of standard antioxidants such as ascorbic acid (Tzankova et al. 2020; Mo et al. 2024). Hydrazones represent a distinct subgroup of Schiff bases, typically synthesized through the condensation of primary amines with active carbonyl compounds. They are considered valuable pharmacophores and versatile intermediates in medicinal chemistry due to their ability to form stable complexes with biological macromolecules and their high reactivity toward free radicals (Ganesh et al. 2024). The azomethine ($-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$) moiety in their structure is believed to play a key role in free radical scavenging and in the stabilization of biological membranes, which may contribute to the protection of hepatocytes from oxidative injury (Bsharat 2023).

The synthesis and neuroprotective antioxidant activity of two new series of hydrazone derivatives, designated as 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e} , were previously reported by our group (Tzankova et al. 2023). In the present study, we systematically evaluated the hepatoprotective and antioxidant potential of compounds 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e} in a set of *in vitro* experimental models. To obtain a comprehensive assessment, several complementary approaches were employed, targeting both enzymatic and non-enzymatic mechanisms of hepatocellular damage. The investigations were performed on isolated rat liver microsomes and hepatocytes, as well as on the human hepatocellular carcinoma cell line HepG2.

Different experimental models were applied to simulate key mechanisms of hepatotoxicity. The non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation model in isolated microsomes was used to evaluate direct antioxidant potential through the inhibition of malondialdehyde (MDA) formation (Palacios et al. 2003). Carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) is one of the most widely used *in vitro* models for studying xenobiotic-induced hepatotoxicity, as it effectively reproduces key cellular mechanisms of oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, and hepatocellular injury (Dua et al. 2023). The t-BuOOH-induced oxidative stress model was applied to evaluate the ability of the compounds to counteract organic hydroperoxide-induced damage in hepatocytes (Miazek et al. 2022), while the H_2O_2 -induced oxidative stress model in HepG2 cells

enabled examination of cellular antioxidant defense mechanisms and overall cytoprotective efficacy (Niu et al. 2025). Evaluation parameters included hepatocyte viability, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage, intracellular GSH content, and MDA levels, representing key indicators of membrane integrity, oxidative balance, and metabolic function.

The aim of the present study was to evaluate the hepatotoxic potential of newly synthesized hydrazone derivatives 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e} and to investigate their possible hepatoprotective effects using a battery of *in vitro* models of liver injury.

Materials and methods

Cell cultures and treatment

The human hepatocellular carcinoma (HepG2) cells were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (ECACC, Salisbury, UK) and maintained in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM, glucose concentration 4.5 g/L), supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum (FBS), 100 U/mL penicillin, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ streptomycin, 1 mM sodium pyruvate, and 2 mM L-glutamine. The cells were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO_2 .

Cytotoxicity assay

HepG2 cells were seeded in 96-well plates at a density of 2×10^4 cells/well and allowed to attach for 24 h at 37 °C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere. The test compounds were prepared in culture medium at final concentrations of 0.1, 1, 5, 10, 50, 100, 250, and 500 μM , and the cells were incubated for 24 h. For each concentration, six replicate wells were used.

After treatment, the medium was replaced with fresh medium containing MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide), dissolved in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at a concentration of 5 mg/mL. The cells were incubated for 3 h, after which the medium was aspirated and the formazan crystals were dissolved in 100 μL dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO). Absorbance was measured using a microplate reader (Synergy 2, BioTek Instruments Inc., Winooski, VT, USA) at 570 nm, with 690 nm used for background correction.

In the oxidative stress model, cells (3.5×10^4 cells/well) were exposed to 0.1 mM H_2O_2 for 1 h to induce submaximal cytotoxicity. To assess protection, cells were pretreated for 1 h with the test compounds (1, 5, and 10 μM) before H_2O_2 exposure. Cell viability was determined 24 h later by the MTT assay. Melatonin (1–10 μM) was used as a reference compound due to its structural similarity to the tested hydrazones and its well-documented antioxidant properties (Chrutek and Olszewska-Slonina 2021).

Animals

Male mice (strain H), with a body weight of 20–30 g, were purchased from the National Breeding Center, Sofia, Bulgaria, and used for all experiments. All procedures were approved by the Bulgarian Food Safety Agency (Permission

No. 323, valid until 22 December 2026) and were conducted in accordance with Ordinance No. 15/2006 for the humane treatment of experimental animals (vivarium certificate of registration No. 0072/01.08.2007). All experiments were performed and reported according to the ARRIVE guidelines (Animal Research: Reporting *In Vivo* Experiments) (Kilkenny et al. 2010) and European regulations for the handling of experimental animals.

Isolation of the rat liver hepatocytes

The isolation of primary hepatocytes was performed using the two-step *in situ* collagenase perfusion method originally described by Fau et al. (1992) and modified by Mitcheva et al. (2006).

On the day of perfusion, two stock buffer solutions (HEPES and Krebs–Ringer bicarbonate, KRB) were freshly prepared. The HEPES buffer (pH 7.85) contained 10 mM HEPES, 142 mM NaCl, 7 mM KCl, and 5 mM D-glucose, while the KRB buffer (pH 7.3) consisted of 1.2 mM KH_2PO_4 , 1.0 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 1.2 mM $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 5 mM KCl, 5 mM NaHCO_3 , and 4.5 mM D-glucose.

Both buffers were continuously gassed with Carbogen (95% O_2 / 5% CO_2) for 30 min and then adjusted to the required pH. The gassing was performed at a low, constant flow rate, as this condition is critical for maintaining normal hepatocyte metabolic activity, including gluconeogenesis, bile acid synthesis, and energy metabolism.

Working solutions were prepared as follows: Solution A—100 mL HEPES supplemented with 0.6 mM EGTA (pH 7.85); Solution B—200 mL HEPES (pH 7.85); Solution C—200 mL HEPES containing 50 mg collagenase and 7 mM $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (pH 7.85). Finally, 500 mL KRB were supplemented with 1% bovine serum albumin (BSA, pH 7.35). The albumin was slowly sprinkled over the surface of the pre-oxygenated solution to avoid foam formation.

From the albumin-containing solution, 60 mL were prewarmed at 37 °C in a water bath, while the remaining volume was stored at 4 °C until use.

Model of metabolic bioactivation induced by carbon tetrachloride

Isolated hepatocytes were incubated with 86 μM carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) dissolved in DMSO (final concentration in the tested samples < 1%), as described by Dianzani et al. (1981), to induce chemical hepatotoxicity and evaluate the protective or modulatory effects of the tested compounds.

Model of t-BuOOH-induced oxidative stress

Isolated hepatocytes were incubated with 75 μM tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH) according to the method of Takayama et al. (2001) to induce oxidative stress and assess the antioxidant and cytoprotective potential of the tested compounds.

Hepatocyte viability assay

Hepatocyte viability was assessed using the trypan blue exclusion assay. Trypan blue is a negatively charged dye that cannot penetrate cells with intact membranes, thus staining only non-viable cells. Consequently, cells excluding the dye were considered viable.

A 0.05% trypan blue solution was freshly prepared, as it is only stable for short-term storage at 4 °C. The stained and unstained hepatocytes were counted under a light microscope at 400× magnification (Fau et al. 1992). The percentage of viable cells was calculated as the ratio of viable to total cells.

Measurement of LDH leakage

Lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity was measured as an indicator of cell membrane integrity and cytotoxic injury. The assay is based on the enzymatic interconversion of lactate and pyruvate, during which NADH is oxidized to NAD^+ . This oxidation results in a measurable decrease in absorbance at 340 nm, reflecting the LDH activity and, consequently, the extent of cell damage.

After incubation with the test substances, hepatocyte suspensions were centrifuged at 400 × g for 3 min, and LDH activity was determined in the supernatant. The samples were stored at –20 °C until analysis. Immediately before measurement, samples were thawed and analyzed according to the manufacturer's protocol for the LDH assay kit. Absorbance was recorded spectrophotometrically at 340 nm at time intervals of 0.5 min, 1 min, 2 min, and 3 min.

GSH level assay

The level of reduced glutathione (GSH) was determined by quantifying the non-protein sulfhydryl (–SH) groups after protein precipitation with 5% trichloroacetic acid (TCA). Thiol groups in the supernatant were measured using Ellman's reagent (5,5'-dithiobis-(2-nitrobenzoic acid), DTNB). Upon reaction with DTNB, thiol groups form a yellow-colored complex with maximum absorbance at 412 nm.

Following incubation, hepatocytes were centrifuged at 4000 × g for 3 min. The supernatant was discarded, and the pellet was treated with 5% TCA and kept on ice for 10 min to ensure complete protein precipitation. Samples were then centrifuged at 8000 × g for 10 min at 20 °C, and the resulting supernatants were stored at –20 °C until analysis.

Immediately before measurement, the samples were thawed and neutralized with 5 N NaOH according to the procedure of Fau et al. (1992).

MDA production in hepatocytes

Lipid peroxidation was assessed by measuring the formation of thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances (TBARS), which are end products of lipid oxidative degradation.

Malondialdehyde (MDA) reacts with 2-thiobarbituric acid (TBA) to form a pink-colored complex consisting of one molecule of MDA and two molecules of TBA. The intensity of the color is directly proportional to the MDA concentration in the sample.

To determine MDA formation, 20% TCA was added to the hepatocyte suspension, which was homogenized and centrifuged at $2000 \times g$ for 5 min. The supernatants were collected, mixed with 0.67% TBA solution, and heated at 100°C for 30 min. After cooling, absorbance of the MDA-TBA complex was measured at 532 nm (Fau et al. 1992).

Isolation of rat liver microsomes

Microsomal fractions were prepared according to the method of Gibson and Skett (1994), with slight modifications. Liver tissue was homogenized in 0.25 M sucrose using a glass-Teflon homogenizer to preserve subcellular integrity. The homogenate was centrifuged at $9000 \times g$ for 30 min at 4°C to remove nuclei and cell debris.

The supernatant was collected, and CaCl_2 (final concentration 8 mM) was added to facilitate microsomal aggregation. The mixture was gently stirred on ice to ensure uniform precipitation of microsomal membranes. The suspension was centrifuged at $24,000 \times g$ for 45 min at 4°C to obtain the microsomal pellet, which was resuspended in 0.1 M Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4). The suspension was kept on ice and either used immediately for assays or aliquoted and stored at -80°C .

Iron/ascorbate-induced lipid peroxidation (LPO) (Mansuy et al. 1986)

Non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation was initiated by freshly prepared FeSO_4 (20 μM) and ascorbic acid (0.5 mM) solutions, which generate reactive oxygen species (ROS) through Fenton-type reactions (Mansuy et al. 1986). The combination of ferrous ions and ascorbate leads to hydroxyl radical formation, resulting in oxidative damage to microsomal membranes and MDA accumulation.

MDA production assay in rat liver microsomes

To each microsomal suspension, 25% TCA was added to ensure protein precipitation. The homogenates were centrifuged at $6000 \times g$ for 10 min at 4°C , and the supernatants were combined with 0.67% TBA solution. The reaction mixtures were heated at 100°C for 30 min and cooled to room temperature. The absorbance of the MDA-TBA complex was then measured at 532 nm, as described by Mansuy et al. (1986).

Data from experiments on isolated rat liver microsomes and hepatocytes were analyzed using MedCalc software. Results were first tested for normality. For normally distributed data, one-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc test was applied; for nonparametric data, the Mann-Whitney U test was used. Statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$. Cell viability results were expressed as mean \pm SD from at least three independent experiments. The viability of untreated control cells was set to 100%, and the survival rate of treated cells was expressed as a percentage of control.

Results

Effects of hydrazone derivatives (series 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}) on isolated rat liver hepatocytes and microsomes

The hepatotoxic potential of hydrazone derivatives 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e} was investigated in isolated rat liver microsomes and hepatocytes to evaluate their potential safety (Table 1).

When administered alone at a concentration of 100 μM , all tested hydrazones from both series (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}) exhibited different grades of hepatotoxic and pro-oxidant effects. These effects were evidenced by a marked decrease in hepatocyte viability and intracellular glutathione (GSH) levels, accompanied by a significant increase in lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage and malondialdehyde (MDA) formation. Among all tested hydrazones, 7d and

Table 1. Effects of two newly synthesized series of hydrazones (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), administered alone at 100 μM , on key biochemical parameters characterizing the functional and metabolic status of isolated rat hepatocytes. Data are expressed as mean \pm SD of three independent experiments. Statistical significance: * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes).

Group	Hepatocytes' viability, %	LDH, $\mu\text{mol}/\text{min}/\text{mill cells}$	GSH, $\text{nmol}/\text{mill cells}$	MDA, $\text{nmol}/\text{mill cells}$
control	85 \pm 4.9	0.101 \pm 0.01	20 \pm 1.4	0.098 \pm 0.01
100 μM 7a	72 \pm 4.9 *	0.225 \pm 0.01 ***	15 \pm 1.1 *	0.155 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 7b	71 \pm 5.1 *	0.236 \pm 0.01 ***	16 \pm 1.2 *	0.198 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 7c	69 \pm 4.8 **	0.258 \pm 0.01 ***	15 \pm 1.1 *	0.177 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 7d	75 \pm 4.8 *	0.158 \pm 0.01 **	18 \pm 1.1 *	0.122 \pm 0.01 **
100 μM 7e	71 \pm 4.9 *	0.241 \pm 0.01 ***	15 \pm 1.2 *	0.169 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 8a	69 \pm 4.8 **	0.228 \pm 0.01 ***	16 \pm 1.2 *	0.178 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 8b	70 \pm 5.1 **	0.238 \pm 0.01 ***	16 \pm 1.4 *	0.166 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 8c	72 \pm 4.9 *	0.244 \pm 0.01 ***	15 \pm 1.4 *	0.159 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 8d	75 \pm 4.8 *	0.161 \pm 0.01 **	18 \pm 1.2 *	0.125 \pm 0.01 ***
100 μM 8e	71 \pm 4.9 *	0.251 \pm 0.01 ***	15 \pm 1.2 *	0.151 \pm 0.01 ***

8d demonstrated the lowest hepatotoxic potential. Treatment with these compounds resulted in only a 10–12% decrease in cell viability and GSH levels, whereas LDH leakage increased by 56–59% and MDA formation by 24–28%, respectively, compared with the control group. Overall, most compounds reduced hepatocyte viability and GSH content by approximately 18–20%, while LDH leakage and MDA production increased by about 140% and 85%, respectively, relative to control cells.

The results indicate that, although most tested hydrazones exhibited, to some extent, pro-oxidant activity in isolated

liver hepatocytes and microsomes, compounds 7d and 8d displayed a comparatively safer profile, suggesting a more favorable balance between biological activity and cellular safety.

When tested on isolated rat liver microsomes, all hydrazones (100 μM) exhibited pronounced pro-oxidant effects compared with the untreated control (Fig. 1). The least pronounced effects were again observed for 7d and 8d (Fig. 1). Most of the compounds caused a statistically significant increase in MDA formation of approximately 38% compared with the control, whereas 7d and 8d increased MDA levels by only 22% and 24%, respectively.

Figure 1. Effects of newly synthesized hydrazone derivatives (series 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), administered alone at 100 μM , on malondialdehyde (MDA) production in isolated rat liver microsomes. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical significance: $p < 0.05$; $p < 0.01$ vs. control (non-treated microsomes).

***In vitro* toxicity evaluation of the newly synthesized compounds in HepG2 cells**

Hepatotoxicity remains one of the leading causes for the withdrawal of drug candidates from both clinical trials and the pharmaceutical market (Giri et al. 2010). To assess the safety profile of the newly synthesized hydrazone derivatives, their effects on the viability of human HepG2 cells were evaluated using the MTT assay. The HepG2 cell line retains many specialized metabolic and enzymatic functions of normal human hepatocytes and thus represents a well-established *in vitro* model for the preliminary screening of hepatotoxicity of chemical compounds, including N-substituted pyrrolyl hydrazones (Noor et al. 2009).

HepG2 cells were treated with compounds 7a, 7b, 7c, 7d, 7e, 8a, 8b, 8c, 8d, and 8e at concentrations ranging from 0.1 to 500 μM . Melatonin (1–10 μM) was used as a reference antioxidant compound. The calculated IC_{50} values are presented in Table 2. Overall, all hydrazones exhibited low or negligible cytotoxicity, with IC_{50} values ranging from 64.28 to 205.10 μM . Notably,

compound 7c displayed the lowest cytotoxicity, with an IC_{50} value above 500 μM , followed by 7a and 8d, with estimated IC_{50} values of 205.10 μM and 198.23 μM , respectively, rendering them the most promising from a safety perspective.

Table 2. IC_{50} values (μM) of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}) determined in HepG2 cells by the MTT assay. Data are presented as mean \pm SD ($n = 3$).

Compound	IC_{50} [μM]	95% confidence interval
7a	205.10	198.64–215.63
7b	98.23	78.01–111.56
7c	> 500	NA
7d	102.38	89.97–114.33
7e	150.23	135.56–163.65
8a	64.28	55.23–76.78
8b	89.98	77.98–123.45
8c	178.32	156.38–199.23
8d	198.23	177.23–218.29
8e	156.35	133.26–175.89
Melatonin	> 500	NA

Effects of hydrazone derivatives (series 7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}, 50 μ M) in combination with hepatotoxic agents on isolated rat liver microsomes and hepatocytes

Under conditions of non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation, all hydrazones (50 μ M) exhibited significant antioxidant activity compared with samples treated with the toxic agent alone (Fig. 2). The protective effect was most pronounced for 7d and 8d. Specifically, 7d and 8d reduced MDA formation by 66% and 64%, respectively, compared with the iron/ascorbate-induced group.

Carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄) represents one of the most widely studied xenobiotic models for hepatocellular injury (Weber et al. 2003). It is bioactivated by cytochrome P450 isoenzymes (CYP1A2, CYP2E1, CYP2B1/B2, CYP3A) to form the trichloromethyl radical (\bullet CCl₃), which initiates lipid peroxidation and thiol oxidation, leading

to membrane disruption and mitochondrial dysfunction. Further oxidation produces the trichloromethylperoxy radical (\bullet OOCCL₃), amplifying oxidative damage and promoting the formation of toxic intermediates such as phosgene (Dianzani et al. 1981; Weber et al. 2003).

When administered alone, CCl₄ caused marked hepatotoxic effects, reducing hepatocyte viability and intracellular GSH levels by 35% and 50%, respectively, and increasing LDH leakage and MDA formation by 152% and 173%, respectively, compared with untreated control hepatocytes.

In the CCl₄-induced hepatotoxicity model, all tested hydrazone derivatives exhibited significant hepatoprotective and antioxidant effects. The compounds preserved hepatocyte viability and GSH levels by approximately 25% and 70%, respectively, and reduced LDH leakage and MDA production by approximately 15% and 35%, respectively, compared with the CCl₄-treated group (Figs 3–6).

Figure 2. Effects of newly synthesized hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μ M, on malondialdehyde (MDA) formation in isolated rat liver microsomes under conditions of iron/ascorbate-induced non-enzymatic lipid peroxidation. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: *p < 0.001 vs. control (non-treated microsomes); ++ p < 0.01, +++ p < 0.001 vs. toxic agent (FeSO₄/ascorbate).

Figure 3. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μ M, on hepatocyte viability in a model of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: p < 0.01 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05 vs. toxic agent (CCl₄).

Figure 4. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μM , on lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage in isolated rat hepatocytes in a model of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: *p < 0.001 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05 vs. toxic agent (CCl₄).

Figure 5. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μM , on intracellular glutathione (GSH) levels in isolated rat hepatocytes under conditions of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: p < 0.01 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05 vs. toxic agent (CCl₄).

Figure 6. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μM , on malondialdehyde (MDA) production in isolated rat hepatocytes under conditions of carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced hepatotoxicity. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: *p < 0.001 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05 vs. toxic agent (CCl₄).

Reactive oxygen species (ROS), such as superoxide anion and hydrogen peroxide, are continuously generated during normal mitochondrial respiration. Excessive ROS accumulation, however, leads to oxidative stress, resulting in lipid, protein, and DNA damage. Tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH) is a widely used *in vitro* inducer of oxidative stress (Karlsson et al. 2000), generating free radicals that initiate lipid peroxidation and deplete intracellular GSH (Kim et al. 1998). The compound also disrupts calcium homeostasis, oxidizes mitochondrial thiol groups, and increases ROS generation, collectively leading to mitochondrial dysfunction and apoptosis (Drahota et al. 2005).

Exposure of hepatocytes to t-BuOOH caused significant toxicity, estimated by a decrease in cell viability and GSH content, accompanied by increased LDH leakage

and MDA formation, confirming its strong cytotoxic potential (Figs 7–10). Treatment with hydrazone derivatives markedly attenuated these effects, with 7d and 8d showing the most pronounced protection. Both compounds effectively preserved cell viability (Fig. 7) and GSH levels (Fig. 9), while reducing lipid peroxidation and LDH release (Fig. 8), indicating robust antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity against t-BuOOH-induced oxidative damage (Figs 7–10). Most probably, the observed hepatoprotective and antioxidant effects of the hydrazone derivatives are associated with their membrane-stabilizing properties, preservation of intracellular GSH, and free radical-scavenging capacity. Among all tested compounds, 7d and 8d consistently showed the strongest protective effects, highlighting them as the most promising candidates for further pharmacological evaluation.

Figure 7. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-c} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 µM, on hepatocyte viability in the model of tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress. Data represent mean ± SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: p < 0.01 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05, ++ p < 0.01 vs. toxic agent (t-BuOOH).

Figure 8. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-c} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 µM, on lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) leakage in isolated rat hepatocytes in the model of tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress. Data represent mean ± SD from three independent experiments (n = 3). Statistical significance: *p < 0.001 vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + p < 0.05, ++ p < 0.01 vs. toxic agent (t-BuOOH).

Figure 9. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μM , on intracellular glutathione (GSH) levels in isolated rat hepatocytes under tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical significance: * $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + $p < 0.05$, ++ $p < 0.01$ vs. toxic agent (t-BuOOH).

Figure 10. Effects of hydrazone derivatives (7_{a-e} and 8_{a-e}), applied at 50 μM , on malondialdehyde (MDA) production in isolated rat hepatocytes under tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH)-induced oxidative stress. Data represent mean \pm SD from three independent experiments ($n = 3$). Statistical significance: * $p < 0.001$ vs. control (non-treated hepatocytes); + $p < 0.05$, ++ $p < 0.01$ vs. toxic agent (t-BuOOH).

Investigation of *in vitro* hepatoprotective effects in HepG2 cells

The potential antioxidant effects of newly synthesized N-pyrrolyl hydrazones were assessed *in vitro* using an H_2O_2 -induced oxidative stress model in HepG2 cells. These effects were evaluated in comparison with melatonin, which served as a reference compound due to its established protective properties. HepG2 cells were pretreated with the tested compounds at concentrations of 1, 5, and 10 μM , followed by exposure to H_2O_2 (as described in the Materials and methods section). The MTT assay was used to assess the effects of the test compounds on mitochondrial function as a marker of cell viability. Exposure to 0.1 μM H_2O_2 for 1 h resulted in a notable reduction in HepG2 cell

viability (Fig. 11). As expected, preincubation with melatonin (1–10 μM) demonstrated concentration-dependent hepatoprotective effects vs. H_2O_2 treatment, as statistically significant preservation of cell viability was observed. Our results showed that compounds **7c**, **7d**, **7e**, **8d**, and **8e** (1–10 μM) possessed statistically significant hepatoprotective effects in this model of oxidative stress (Fig. 11). Interestingly, compounds **7e** and **8d** showed higher protection than the reference compound melatonin. As shown, **7e** significantly reduced H_2O_2 -induced cell damage, increasing cell viability by 45%, 56%, and 45%, respectively, while **8d** demonstrated statistically significant protection of 41%, 63%, and 55%, respectively. The test compounds **7a**, **7b**, **8a**, **8b**, and **8c** did not produce any hepatoprotective effects in HepG2 cells at the tested concentrations (data not shown).

Figure 11. Protective effects of hydrazone derivatives (7c, 7d, 7e, 8d, and 8e) and melatonin (1–10 µM) in a model of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 0.1 mM)-induced oxidative damage in HepG2 cells. HepG2 cells were pretreated with the compounds (1, 5, and 10 µM) for 1 h prior to H₂O₂ exposure, and viability was assessed by the MTT assay. Data represent mean ± SD from three independent experiments (n = 8). Statistical significance: p < 0.01; p < 0.001 vs. H₂O₂ group (one-way ANOVA with Dunnett's post hoc test).

Discussion

The *in vitro* evaluation of the newly synthesized N-pyrrolyl hydrazone derivatives provides valuable insights into the relationship between chemical structure and hepatoprotective activity. Across the two series of compounds tested, 7d and 8d consistently exhibited superior safety and protective profiles, suggesting that the presence of a free OH group at the *p*-position on the phenyl part of the structure is critical for modulating biological activity. This emphasizes the importance of structure–activity relationships in guiding the rational design of hydrazone derivatives with optimized therapeutic indices.

The hepatoprotective activity of 7d and 8d appears to involve multiple and complementary mechanisms. Both compounds effectively preserved intracellular glutathione (GSH) levels, a key determinant of redox homeostasis and cellular defense against reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Ray et al. 2012). By preventing GSH depletion, 7d and 8d strengthen endogenous antioxidant capacity and reduce the vulnerability of hepatocytes to oxidative injury. Furthermore, both derivatives significantly inhibited lipid peroxidation, as evidenced by reduced malondialdehyde (MDA) formation in hepatocyte and microsomal models. This attenuation of lipid peroxidation suggests a stabilizing effect on cellular and organellar membranes, particularly within mitochondria and the endoplasmic reticulum, which are highly susceptible to ROS-induced damage.

The protective properties of 7d and 8d were consistent across multiple models of hepatotoxicity. In the carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄)-induced model, bioactivation of CCl₄ via cytochrome P450 enzymes generates

trichloromethyl (•CCl₃) and trichloromethylperoxy (•OOCCL₃) radicals, initiating lipid peroxidation, membrane disruption, and calcium imbalance (Dianzani et al. 1981; Weber et al. 2003). Treatment with 7d and 8d markedly mitigated these effects, maintaining cell viability and GSH levels while reducing LDH leakage and MDA accumulation, thus limiting oxidative and necrotic injury. Similarly, in the tert-butyl hydroperoxide (t-BuOOH) model, which induces oxidative stress via radical formation, GSH depletion, and mitochondrial dysfunction (Kim et al. 1998; Drahota et al. 2005), both derivatives attenuated ROS generation, stabilized cell membranes, and prevented apoptosis.

The HepG2 cell line serves as an appropriate tool for investigating the cytoprotective properties of different substances, both natural and synthetic. Its reliability and versatility make it a preferred choice for researchers aiming to understand cellular responses to various compounds and to assess their potential therapeutic benefits. By using HepG2 cells, valuable insights can be gained into the mechanisms underlying cytoprotection, and the efficacy of compounds in mitigating cellular damage and promoting cell viability can be evaluated (Lv et al. 2019). In the hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂)-induced oxidative stress model in HepG2 cells, 7d and 8d exhibited pronounced cytoprotective effects, in some cases exceeding those of melatonin, a well-established reference antioxidant. These results underscore the ability of the compounds to counteract both direct chemical toxicity and ROS-mediated oxidative stress, demonstrating a broad spectrum of hepatoprotective activity across diverse cellular systems.

Mechanistically, 7d and 8d likely act through a synergistic combination of radical scavenging, membrane stabilization, and preservation of mitochondrial function, in line with previous reports on multifunctional antioxidants (Ji et al. 2019). By limiting lipid peroxidation, they prevent the formation of secondary reactive aldehydes, such as 4-hydroxynonenal (4-HNE), which can form covalent adducts with proteins, impair enzymatic function, and amplify cellular injury. Preservation of mitochondrial integrity prevents excessive calcium influx, maintains ATP synthesis, and reduces apoptotic signaling (Zhang et al. 2022), all of which are commonly associated with xenobiotic-induced oxidative stress.

The observed structure–activity relationship provides a rationale for the superior efficacy of 7d and 8d due to the presence of a free OH group in their structure. This substituent may enhance electron delocalization or introduce steric and conformational features that facilitate interactions with radicals and membrane lipids, leading to more efficient antioxidant and hepatoprotective activity. These findings suggest that subtle modifications of the hydrazone scaffold can significantly alter both safety and efficacy, emphasizing the importance of careful structural optimization in drug design.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that among the tested hydrazone derivatives, 7d and 8d exhibit the most favorable hepatoprotective and antioxidant profiles. Their efficacy appears to be mediated through preservation of intracellular glutathione (GSH), inhibition of lipid peroxidation, stabilization of cellular membranes, and maintenance of mitochondrial function. The observed structure–activity relationship indicates that d-substitution plays a crucial role in enhancing radical scavenging capacity and membrane interactions. These findings support the potential of 7d and 8d as lead compounds for further preclinical development of novel hepatoprotective agents. Their ability to mitigate both oxidative and chemically induced stress across multiple experimental models underscores their promise for future therapeutic applications in liver diseases and conditions associated with oxidative injury.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

Use of commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines: HepG2 cell line (ECACC, Sigma Aldrich).

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

This study was financed by the European Union—NextGenerationEU through the National Recovery and Resilience Plan of the Republic of Bulgaria, project No. BG-RRP-2.004-0004-C01.

Author contributions

A.G. (Alime Garip) – investigation, experimental work, data curation, visualization, writing – original draft preparation, writing – review & editing, coordination of manuscript preparation. M.K.-B. (Magdalena Kondeva-Burdina) – supervision, conceptualization of toxicological experiments, methodology, investigation, data interpretation, writing – review & editing. D.S. (Denitsa Stefanova) – writing – original draft (toxicological part), methodological support, data interpretation, writing – review & editing. D.T. (Diana Tzankova) – chemical synthesis of the hydrazone derivatives, structural characterization, preparation of chemical descriptions in the manuscript, writing – review. M.G. (Maya Georgieva) – chemical synthesis support, analytical characterization, verification of chemical data, writing – review. V.T. (Virginia Tzankova) – supervision, final critical revision of the manuscript, scientific guidance, writing – review & editing.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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